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CONCEPTUALIZATION OF PROFESSIONAL DEVELOPMENT OF TEACHERS

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ABSTRACT

Education is prime responsibility of any society. It needs to uncultured their children. This responsibility is majorly fulfilled by teachers as a prime instrument. Between teachers and students, a well designed curriculum is transacted using skills, strategies and teaching methods. Transaction of curriculum to students is something which require skilled strategies and methods according to psychological state of students, organizational climate and nature of content. This skill of transaction of content is the basic requirement for the professional development of teachers. We could say it as "Language of Teaching" as without knowing language one is unable to communicate how & what he wants to. This research paper is an attempt to explore need, importance, challenges and suggestions for professional development of teachers.

KEYWORDS: *Professional Development, Teachers, Challenges, Teaching Skills.*

INTRODUCTION

"Those who educate children well are more to be honoured than they who produce them; for these only gave them life, those arts of living well."

- Aristotle

Teachers are considered to be the builder of the nation. In other words, the future of the nation lies in the hands of teacher. One can realize how important education is which makes one a teacher. Teaching is a profession-indeed a noble one, conceptual and ideal. It is also different from other professions because it is engaged in human development activities. It is only in the case of teaching there is much more that is required to be accomplished than in the case

of other professions. Training of the teachers on regular interval is considered to be one of the important characteristics of their professional development.

Concept of Professional Development:

According to the thesaurus of the Educational Resources Information Center (ERIC) database, professional development refers to “activities to enhance professional career growth.” Such activities may include individual development, continuing education, and in-service education, as well as curriculum writing, peer collaboration, study groups, and peer coaching or mentoring. As the definition of, “Professional Growth” is given in the Dictionary of Education by Carter V. Good; Professional Growth means increase in subject matter knowledge, teaching Skills and efficiency and insight in to educational problems with a concomitant increase in success a teacher. Professional development, in a broad sense refers to the development of a person in his professional role. According to Ganser (2000) Professional development includes formal experiences such as attending workshops and professional meeting and mentoring etc. and informal experiences such as reading professional publications, watching television documentaries related to an academic discipline etc. According to Glatthorn (1995) the conception of professional development is therefore broader than career development, which is defined as “the growth that occurs as the teacher moves through the professional cycle”. According to Kedzior and Fifield (2004) effective professional development is a prolonged facet of classroom instruction that is integrated, logical and on-going and incorporates experiences that are consistent with teachers’ goals; aligned with standards, assessments, other reform initiatives, and beset by the best research evidence. Odebero, (2010) described professional development as sustained focus over time that is consistent with best practice. Joyce & Showers (2002) stated that the Process of Professional Development Professional development should be designed around research-documented practices that enable educators to develop the skills necessary to implement what they are learning.

Many professional such as teachers, professors, army officers, health care professionals, lawyers, accountants and engineers engage in professional development. Individuals may engage in professional development because of his interest in continuous learning, to improve professional ability, accelerate career progression and to adapt new technologies and practices. Professional development means skills and knowledge gained for both personal development and career advancement. There are various ways for professional development of teachers like orientation programs, refresher courses, seminars, conferences, consultation, coaching, lesson study, mentoring, reflective supervision and technical assistance etc. Professional development may also come in the form of pre-service or in-service professional development programs. These programs may be formal, or informal, group or individualized. Individuals may pursue professional development independently, or programs may be offered by human resource departments. Professional development on the job may develop or enhance process skills, sometimes referred to as leadership skills, as well as task skills.

Types of professional development:

- Orientation Programs (For newly appointed teachers of higher education)
- Refresher Courses (on subjects matters)
- Faculty Induction Programs
- Online courses (SWAYAM, ARPIT etc)

- Workshops (e.g. on subject matter or methodology of content-related topics)
- Educational Conferences or Seminars (at which teachers and/or researchers present their research results and discuss education problems)
- Qualification Programs (e.g. a degree or diploma programs)
- Observation visits to other institutions
- Individual or collaborative research on a topic of educational interest
- Reading related literature to their area of research work. (e.g. journals, evidence-based papers, research-thesis)
- Active feedback from students and colleagues on improvement of teaching.

Need of professional development of teachers:

Quality of education is depends upon quality of the teachers. Thus role of teachers is very important in shaping future generation. All the commissions and committees always emphasized the need of professional development of the teachers. Policies in India supporting professional development of teachers are following:

Mudaliar Commission report pointed out that “We are convinced that most important factor in contemplated educational reconstruction is the teacher, his personal qualities, his educational qualification, his professional training and the place he occupies in the community”. No doubt for professional development of teachers professional training of the teachers is one of the gross root requirement however, different commissions suggested different programs for the professional development of teachers.

National Educational Commission (1964-66) suggested that for the professional development of teachers orientation programs are very important and also recommended that in-service training for teachers should be organised by universities and allow every teacher to receive 2-3 months of in-service training once in five years.

National Policy on Education (1986) and Program of Action (1992):

National Policy on Education 1986 in its Program of Action states that-

- To organize specially designed orientation program for all new appointed teachers.
- To organize orientation program for the teachers.
- To organize refresher courses for the teachers at least once in five years.
- To encourage teachers to participate in workshops, seminars, and conference etc.

Mehrotra Committee (1987) (Revision of Pay Scales of Teachers in University) suggested orientated program of 3-4 weeks for the freshly appointed teachers. The emphasis should be laid on the methodologies of teaching in the concerned subject.

Ramamurthy Committee (1990) recommended that there should be one year training after appointment of the teachers for their professional development.

Importance of Professional Development:

According to Joyce and Showers (2002) for effective professional development programmes should be based on curricular and instructional strategies that have a high probability of affecting students' ability to learn and in turn students' learning achievement. In addition, professional development broaden and deepens teachers' subject matter knowledge and contributes in new

knowledge to the profession. It enrich teachers' knowledge of the subject's content and sharpen teaching skills and classroom skills. It contributes new knowledge to the profession and increases the ability of teachers to monitor student work and make them capable to identified gaps in student achievement. It supports interaction among master teachers that takes place over extended periods of time. It provides opportunities for teachers to try skills and strategies in classroom and receive feedback from students and peers.

Challenges to Professional Developments:

Studies show that many challenges exist with regard to successful implementation of professional development. Parvez, M. (2009) explained barriers to fulfilment of professional development include time, accessibility, staff motivation, marketing and advertising, and financial issues. According to Ian, H. (2010) age, staff shortages, unsupportive managers, staff attitude, availability of programs, work pressure, family commitments, unsafe environments, and participation on own time are also identified as barriers. Generally there are many challenges in professional development of teachers. The three major categories of barriers of professional development are as follows:

Psychological barriers: In the process of professional development, college teachers often have psychological barriers due to various problems. Some of the psychological barriers are teachers lacking positive attitude and motivation, interest, confidence, lacking awareness and reluctant to learn new techniques and technologies and teachers having stress and frustration.

Administrative barriers: Teachers faces many administrative barrierstoacquire professional development like, poor administration and government policies, lack of physical & financial facilities, inadequate time & funding.

Material barriers: In quality professional development teachers faces various material barriers like time commitments, energy demands, work environment, family support.

Recommendations for educational institutions:

- The educational institutions should encourage the teachers to acquire higher degrees. It will help to enhance the profession knowledge of the teachers.
- Organizing regular professional development programs like orientation programs, refresher courses and invite subject wise experts for the seminar and workshops will help teachers to learn new skills and new teaching technique.
- Financial assistance should be given to the teachers to undertake research work and projects related to teaching-learning process.
- The private schools management should encourage teachers to actively participate in workshops, seminars and similar professional development programs organized by the education department.

Recommendations for teachers:

- The teachers themselves should show keen interest in acquiring higher degrees.
- Teachers should properly utilize the available resources and acquire new skills and technique by attending periodical professional development programs, refresher courses, meeting the subject wise experts, seminar and workshops.

CONCLUSION:

Teachers play a pivotal role in the improvement of the quality of education. Education is a continuous process and no formal training in an institution can fully prepare a person for professional service. The continuous learning is important as teachers knowledge lags behind due to continuous expansion of knowledge in the field of teacher education on a regular basis. Hence, the training of the teachers carries special importance. Professional development of a teacher implies his mastery in knowledge of the subject, in pedagogy and teaching techniques. In assessment of the educational system, it is necessary to know whether there are sufficient teachers, who are not only well qualified to teach their subject contents, but are also able keep pace with the changing curriculum, develop innovative methods, strategies and pedagogies of teaching and growth in knowledge. It is crucial to know about the facilities that exist for improving their knowledge and enhancing their teaching skills. Therefore, in order to befit the teachers to their roles, a good professional training is required. Faculty induction program and continuous education thereafter equips the teachers with adequate knowledge and skills to perform their professional functions.

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